

The US Extremely Large Telescope Program

Mark Dickinson (NSF's NOIRLab)

Many of today's forefront astronomical problems demand higher angular resolution and greater sensitivity than 8–10m optical–infrared telescopes can provide. [The US Extremely Large Telescope Program](#) (US-ELTP) will deliver those capabilities, opening new frontiers in nearly all areas of astrophysics, from solar systems (our own and around other stars) to cosmology. The large apertures and small diffraction limits of Extremely Large Telescopes (ELTs) will enable dramatic advances in the investigation of the forefront problems of the decades to come and open tremendous potential for new discoveries. For diffraction-limited observations, sensitivity¹ scales with telescope primary mirror diameter (D) as D^4 , or even more steeply for observations in crowded fields, so the potential gains from telescopes with $D > 20\text{m}$ are enormous.

The US-ELTP is a partnership between [NSF's NOIRLab](#) and the organizations building the [Giant Magellan Telescope](#) (GMT) and the [Thirty Meter Telescope](#) (TMT). Our aim is to complete construction of a bi-hemispheric ELT system available to all US scientists, regardless of their institutional affiliations. We seek to provide 25% or greater shares of national open-access observing time on both the TMT and the GMT, available via NOIRLab's peer-reviewed time allocation process. Any US astronomer with a great idea will be able to propose to use these world-class facilities to study objects anywhere on the sky, using a broader suite of instruments than a single observatory could provide. The observing time available to US astronomers will enable Key Science Programs (KSPs) to tackle fundamental problems requiring dedicated effort using large, multiyear allocations of GMT and TMT observing time, as well as smaller, focused Discovery Science Programs allocated on a more frequent cadence, nimble and responsive to new opportunities and new ideas. NOIRLab will provide a suite of user services spanning the full research life cycle from proposal preparation through data analysis and publication, ensuring inclusive support for a broad community of observers and archival researchers.

The recent Decadal Survey report, *Pathways to Discovery in Astronomy and Astrophysics for the 2020s*, wrote: “Because of the transformative potential that large (20–40m) telescopes with diffraction-limited adaptive optics have for astronomy, and because of the readiness of the projects, the survey committee's top recommendation for frontier ground-based observatories is investment in the US ELT Program. [...] These observatories will create enormous opportunities for scientific progress over the coming decades and well beyond, and they will address nearly every important science question across all three priority science themes.” The three Decadal Survey science themes and the importance of US-ELTP capabilities for addressing each are as follows:

- **Worlds and Suns in Context:** The study of exoplanetary systems including their formation and evolution and the interconnections between planets and their host stars.
 - **Priority science area:** *Pathways to Habitable Worlds* — the quest to identify and study potentially habitable planets and to seek atmospheric chemical indicators of habitability and perhaps life itself.
 - **Role of the US-ELTP:** Resolving forming and mature planetary systems, spectroscopic analysis of those systems and of exoplanet atmospheres, and the search for chemical biosignatures.
- **New Messengers and New Physics:** The application of multi-messenger astrophysics and time-domain astronomy to address fundamental questions in cosmology and physics.
 - **Priority science area:** *New Windows on the Dynamic Universe* — using temporal observations of gravitational waves and electromagnetic radiation to address fundamental questions about black holes, neutron stars, and the explosive consequences of their interactions and mergers.
 - **Role of the US-ELTP:** Precision measurements to resolve the physics of dark matter and accelerating cosmic expansion, test the nature of gravity near supermassive black holes, and conduct time-resolved and time-critical measurements of the faint electromagnetic counterparts to gravitational wave beacons created by merging compact objects.

¹ Here, sensitivity is defined as the reciprocal of the exposure time required to attain a given signal-to-noise ratio for observations of a point source with a given flux in the background-limited regime.

- **Cosmic Ecosystems:** The integrated study of gas, stars, and black holes within galaxies and their interconnections over a huge dynamic range of scale and density — processes that shape the evolving life cycle of galaxies, their contents, and the intergalactic medium.
 - **Priority science area:** *Unveiling the Hidden Drivers of Galaxy Growth* — direct observations of galaxies and circum- and inter-galactic gas to understand the cosmic “baryon cycle” that governs the growth and evolution of galaxies and their component structures over cosmic history.
 - **Role of the US-ELTP:** Spatially resolved observations of early galaxies and their intersellar and circumgalactic gaseous media, and analysis of today’s fossil record using resolved stellar populations in galaxies throughout the Local Volume.

The bi-hemispheric US-ELTP supporting these next-generation observatories and their state-of-the-art instrumentation will enable research breakthroughs in all of these science areas, as well as capability for unexpected discoveries anywhere on the sky. Two telescopes will ensure full sky coverage with approximately 50% sky overlap where the complementary capabilities and instruments of the GMT and TMT can be used together. The longitudinal separation of the telescopes will support and enhance critical time-domain science programs. Two telescopes will ensure that more observing nights are available to enable US astronomers to carry out large-scale KSPs. US-ELTP capabilities will work together with all-sky space observatories on the problems of the future, as well as with other forefront observatories operating at all wavelengths in both hemispheres, and all-sky multimessenger facilities such as the next generation of gravitational wave detectors. The US-ELTP leverages the past

Figure 1. The US Extremely Large Telescope Program will enable US astronomers to observe objects anywhere in the sky using the Thirty Meter Telescope (left) in the northern hemisphere and Giant Magellan Telescope (right) in the southern hemisphere. Credit: US-ELTP (Giant Magellan Telescope/NOIRLab/TMT)

and present capital and intellectual investment by the current TMT and GMT partners and integrates the whole US research community into these trans-Pacific, multi-continental, international partnerships, establishing an unparalleled worldwide ELT collaboration.

In addition to serving as a gateway for US community observing proposals for the GMT and TMT, NOIRLab will provide a full suite of user support services and tools, drawing on the extensive heritage of all of NOIRLab's programs and observatories and building new capabilities optimized for the needs of the TMT, GMT, and US-ELTP user community. NOIRLab's US ELT Program Platform will span all stages of the "science data life cycle," including observing proposal preparation, observing time allocation, observing program planning, dynamic and adaptive observation scheduling, data archiving, data reduction, and data analysis. All GMT and TMT data will be archived at NOIRLab and will be available after agreed-upon proprietary periods. Science data obtained using standard observing procedures and calibrations will undergo pipeline processing, and reduced, calibrated data products will be archived. NOIRLab will provide and support data analysis tools in a science platform environment that facilitates collaboration within teams and archival research using TMT/GMT data.

NOIRLab has established a small but dynamic team that is working closely with the GMT and TMT projects and the US science community to bring the US-ELTP to fruition. The current Project Director is Beth Willman, and the Project Manager is Steven Berukoff, who recently joined NOIRLab from the National Solar Observatory. Mark Dickinson and Marie Lemoine-Busserolle are the Project Scientist and Systems Scientist, respectively. In a nutshell, they are responsible for ensuring that NOIRLab's user services and tools will meet the research needs of a diverse astronomical community. Dara Norman (also deputy director of NOIRLab's Community Science and Data Center, CSDC) and research associate Tim Sacco are the US-ELTP's Research Inclusion Team, guiding NOIRLab's plan to ensure that NOIRLab's US-ELTP policies and user services will provide outstanding

and equitable support for a community of users from a wide variety of institutional backgrounds, including scientists at small and under-resourced institutions. The newest team member is André-Nicolas Chené, Community Engagement Scientist, who will oversee NOIRLab's efforts to inform, consult, and involve the scientific community in planning and development of the US-ELTP, working closely with the Research Inclusion Team. Andrew Serio is the Project Systems Engineer, responsible for developing and maintaining the project's formal requirements and their traceability from use cases and for developing and overseeing verification and validation of the user support software systems. Other US-ELTP team members include Sharon Hunt (Document Manager), Kevin Long (Project Controls Specialist), Mark Newhouse (Communications, Education & Engagement Liaison), and Stephen Ridgway (Technical Monitor). The core team also draws on the tremendous resource of expertise in other NOIRLab programs, particularly in CSDC and Gemini.

In recent years, community scientists have contributed enormously to the development of the US-ELTP, formulating KSP concepts that demonstrate the potential of a bi-hemispheric ELT system, and writing white papers on the transformational science that the system will enable. The Decadal Survey endorsement is, in no small part, a consequence of our community's enthusiasm and effort. With that endorsement, the US-ELTP partnership is now preparing proposals for peer review at the National Science Foundation to support the development and construction of the observatories and NOIRLab's suite of user services. NOIRLab and the TMT and GMT projects will continue to work with the astronomical community to understand its needs for observatory capabilities, future instrumentation, and user support, and to inform the community about scientific opportunities and the status and progress of the program and the observatories. The upcoming June AAS meeting #240 in Pasadena, California, home to both the GMT and TMT project offices, will be one of many future opportunities to learn about the US-ELTP and to meet staff from both observatories and NOIRLab. Look for more information about the US-ELTP in [e-News for the NOIRLab Community](#).

NSF's NOIRLab

A spectacular portrait of the galaxy Centaurus A is captured using the Dark Energy Camera mounted on the Victor M. Blanco 4-meter Telescope at Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory in Chile. This galaxy's peculiar appearance — cloaked in dark tendrils of dust — stems from a past interaction with another galaxy, and its size and proximity to Earth make it one of the best-studied giant galaxies in the night sky. *Credit: CTIO/NOIRLab/DOE/NSF/AURA*

Acknowledgment

*PI: M. Soraisam (University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign/
NSF's NOIRLab)*